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Introducing Engineering Essence in Liberal Arts Education in Japanese University

Engineering in Liberal Arts and Liberal Arts in Engineering

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1. INTRODUCTION

In Japan the liberal arts education is expected to be an important element to promote innovation and bring the economy back to prosperity again. Technological invention is indispensable for the innovation, but that is not enough in nowadays. Identifying the subterranean market needs behind flood of information is also important for the successful innovation. The liberal arts education is believed as an essential mean to help the understanding the global market and to communicate with people who has different cultural back ground. Steve Jobs pointed out the importance of liberal arts, saying “It is in Apple’s DNA that technology alone is not enough—it’s technology married with liberal arts, married with the humanities, that yields us the results that make our heart sing.”

Moreover, it is necessary to resolve social conflict associated with introduction of new technologies. It requires both expert’s social literacy and non-expert’s science and technology literacy. In this paper, two approaches to investigate how to incorporate the engineering to general liberal arts education, as well as the necessity of liberal arts education in engineering education, are discussed.

2. LIBERAL ARTS EDUCATION IN JAPAN.

The origin of the liberal arts can be back to ancient Greek scholars' work, In European medieval period, seven subjects; grammar, rhetoric, logic, arithmetic, geometric, music and astronomy, consisted classical liberal arts education. It is believed they were to foster independent and judicious citizen and that technology was just skill transferred in apprentice system.

There are many published articles discussing the issues on liberal arts education in Japan[1]. Rie Mori has introduced briefly current situation and historical context[2]. The author is looking the situation as follows from engineering education perspective. The meaning of liberal arts has been changing in Japanese higher education system, since European modern knowledge was introduced in the mid-19th century. It may somewhat have a slight or significant difference from that in European countries. What Japanese had intended to introduce was practical application of science, without the core philosophical idea to understand the whole world. It is clearly shown in the Japanese translation of "science"; "KA-GAKU". That literally means studies of independent disciplines.

The liberal arts education in Japanese universities underwent atrophy in 1990th century, but is reviving recently. Let's review Japanese liberal arts history briefly. In Japanese education system before World War II, the liberal arts education was conducted in three years in senior high school. The senior high school education at that time was assigned as preparatory education for university, in which education system was designed to foster higher professionals. It was consisted with foreign languages, humanities, social and natural science, and they emphasized enlightening humanities. At that period, the number of university students was very limited. Only a few percent of the young generation had a chance to study such liberal arts.

After WWII, education system reform was conducted, after American system. The former senior high school was consolidated to new university and college system. Foreign languages, basic natural and social science, and humanities were placed as compulsory course in the first two year of the university. For example, a student in an engineering course had to study several subjects in humanities, social and natural science, and foreign languages respectively. It was said as general education, as well as liberal arts education. While university entrance rate was rising, importance of general (liberal arts) education was not well understood among students, regarding as useless knowledge or just repetition of high school education. In 1991, the ministry of education reformed the rule for university curriculum, and most university contracted the general (liberal) education to promote higher professional or interdisciplinary studies. However, recently, the liberal arts education is getting

arrestive and reviving as effective way to educate innovators and entrepreneurs, as described in the introduction.

3. ENGINEERING EDUCATION FOR INNOVATION

According to the innovation policy of Japanese government, it is expected to strengthen the tight between basic academic research and social implementation by the education. It is pointed out that the liberal arts education is keen to develop innovation leaders. The Japan Federation of Engineering Societies [3] insisted the importance of promoting connoisseur's eyes to identify social and economic value, as well as technological invention. They also emphasized the role of management in innovations. The training of this ability was not included in traditional Japanese engineering education. And it needs collaboration with people who have no engineering background. Thus, new approaches, such as Problem/Project Based Learning, or design oriented, are noticed. They are to build up communication skill of students, and to found wide range of liberal arts knowledge.

The conventional engineering education in Japan have taught how to make things but not what to make. In other words, the purpose of engineering has never been dealt with in Japanese engineering education. The decision making is based on their value standard, but natural science, including technology or engineering, is on neutral ground to the values in society. The Engineer should know how such value is formed. Thus, new type of education for engineers is required in Japan.

There is a book titled "KYOYOU NO KOUGAKU"[4]; "Engineering of Liberal arts", if translated into English directly. It is written for medical school students who are studying rehabilitation. Mechanics, materials, measurement, indoor environment, process management and human error are included. That is published for special student, but could be one of the ways to go.

Integration of engineering and liberal education was discussed in many universities in US, to foster innovative and entrepreneurial capacity in engineering undergraduate students by a liberal arts education.[5]

4. TRANS-SCIENCE AND LITERACIES

Social implementation of advanced technologies, such as genetic manipulation, often brings about people's anxiety. A.M.Weinberg defined "Trans-Science", as "questions which can be asked of science and yet which cannot be answered by science." [6] The scientist and engineers tend to take enlightening approach, but it does no work well for the technological risk issue. Collaboration between the experts and non-experts to reach an agreement is essential, because science cannot lead a solution. The experts tend to require people to have rigid and precise understanding.

The social acceptance is another issue. The experts, scientists and engineers, should know the non-experts' way of thinking. Various methodologies have been developed to make citizen's participation in technology assessment. Consensus conference is one of the well-known examples in Japan.

From the view point of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), although fairness in scientific research activity has been mainly discussed in Japan, little has been said about responsible innovation. It will be required to conduct innovation in responsible way to accord with UN's Sustainable Development Goals.

The engineers, as well as other experts, need to develop their accountability to not only their clients but also wide range of stake holders, concerning to the value and risk of their achievements. At the same time, literacy of experts on social and cultural aspects is needed to explain their accountability. Generally, development of the literacy of non-experts is requested for the decision making on such socio-technical issues.

5. ENGINEERING IN LIBERAL ARTS

As previously mentioned, the liberal arts are activities to understand what the real whole world is. When one looks at today's world, it never exists without technology. So, engineering or technology should be included in the liberal arts. Like students in science and engineering should study social literacy, engineering literacy for non-engineering students should be developed.

There are quite a few such subjects, as far as the author has looked into in the curriculums of Japanese major universities. One of them is "Introduction to modern technology" in the University of Tokyo. An appointed professor in an engineering department lecture on the outline of their research activity and the relationship with society.[7] It is certainly good and realistic practice, but still limited in a specific engineering field, and it is designed for engineering and science students.

Based on the discussion in the previous sections, two approaches should be included in liberal arts. One is fundamental engineering knowledge and the other is framework in engineer's activity.

5.1. Fundamentals in Engineering

Nowadays, the technological products is getting so integrated and complex that an engineer has to have wide range of technological and scientific knowledge. An engineering expert can be just a non-expert in other engineering field. Since it is quite hard to study all technological elements and the engineering knowledge is

expanding rapidly, comprehensive and compact fundamental and systematic knowledge in the engineering is desired.

There are substantial numbers of classes named basic engineering or engineering literacy, in which lessons in mathematics, errors, units, drafting, descriptive geometry, dynamics, electromagnetics, or materials science are given to engineering students. Those engineering literacy classes are designed only for engineers, although science literacy is often designed for every people. It should be noticed that some of such science literacy is containing technology as well.[8] In such case, it is necessary to emphasize the deference between science and engineering (technology) . They have own their origins and purposes. Mixing up those two would mislead what the non-experts expect on them.

If such knowledge system is well developed, it will be easy to identify what is possible by technology, and pseudo-scientific dream and non-realistic technology are eliminated. Unfortunately, it is still just in the starting point of discussion.

5.2. Framework of Engineer's Conducts

Engineers are struggling with various problems for better design or manufacturing. It is desirable that non-engineering people know the nature of the problems which engineers are facing with. They are different from those of scientists. They are determining the engineer's way of thinking and design.

(1) Compromising trade-offs between cost, quality and delivery

Engineers are requested to improve quality, to decrease cost and to shorten delivery. Those are conflicting with each other. The engineers should manage the balance satisficing their customer's demands. They have another trade-offs in improving the qualities, because there are plural inconsistent properties. Many technological failures are due to mismanagement of the balance.

(2) Heterogeneous objects

Natural raw materials, whatever they are organic or inorganic, are not homogeneous. Their composition, surface structure, strength, and etc. are changing with location and time. But engineers have to make almost same products using such heterogeneous materials, which do not show theoretical behaviour. It is inevitable to apply safety factor to ensure the quality or safety. To make things worse, every material is unavoidable from deterioration by corrosion or decomposition.

(3) Dealing with uncertainty

In general the boundary conditions for design are determined by the customer. It means that the engineers have a degree of freedom and responsibility as well. Sometime the boundary conditions are not well defined and vague. Furthermore,

sometimes the phenomena which are controlling the working mechanism of the product is not scientifically understand well, and the engineers has to design without necessary information. As the result, engineer's calculation tends to be in an overestimation to the theoretical value, applying empirical coefficients.

(4) Multiple solutions

Based on the uncertainty mentioned above, engineers do not always lead unique answer. There could be another solution, and the best answer is depending on the case and often not found.

(5) To make mistakes is human

Engineers are requested to prepare for misuse of the customer, as well as engineers' mistake. They have to imagine whatever possible. And engineers are also human to make mistake.

The concept of engineering in liberal arts is schematically shown in figure1.

Fig. 1. Schematic Illustration of the Concept of Engineering as Liberal Arts

6. CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this paper two approaches are proposed to incorporate engineering into liberal arts education. One is to develop compact but comprehensive engineering fundamental theory. And the other is to clarify the frameworks which determine engineer's conduct. The establishment of the specific contents is still future work. It is expected to develop public understanding of engineering, and to form social ability to select appropriate technology systems. A working group in Japanese Society for Engineering Education has been established and started discussion. There are several examples such as history of technology, including accidents and failures, or PBL type activity to solve local issues. The contents, introduced in section 5.1 and 5.2 in this paper are under intensive discussion, and expected to put into a practice plan in a few years.

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